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SERVICE STRATEGIES INFLUENCE ON THE QUALITY OF BEAUTY INDUSTRY COMPANIES THAT INCREASE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

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Abstract

The modern standard of living puts forward new requirements for the health, appearance of a person, as well as for the level of service offered. One of the global trends of the modern economy is the dynamic growth of the services market. The service sector has a very noticeable impact on the level and quality of life of the society. The structure of the domestic market of services is undergoing significant changes, the role of service industries is constantly increasing, work in companies that provide services is becoming more and more prestigious, meeting the requirements of international and European standards.

Keywords: service, quality, beauty industry, service strategy, competitive advantage.

The problems of the service are quite typical for any complex case. High-quality service requires highly qualified employees, and significant funds must be spent on training these personnel. We need a special type of employee — a highly qualified all-rounder with extraordinary psychological and personal qualities, since we are talking about constant contact with consumers.

Today, marketing is successfully used in the service sector, but previously it was almost not used in the service of everyday life. Marketing is a process designed to help others evaluate services, evaluate what is being done for customers, and how it is being done. The main goal of service marketing is to help the client appreciate the organization's services, and the most difficult aspect of service marketing is to create favorable conditions for the provision of these services. The intangible nature of the services, their elusiveness, or their immaterial nature means that they cannot be demonstrated, seen, or tried before receiving these services (Wangnanon, W. and Saomoung, S. 2012). In any service activity, the buyer is to some extent a participant in this process. The quality of the service depends quite significantly on who provides it. When organizing service activities, it is necessary to take into account the needs of customers. The consumer's perception of the services is important. In the competition and competition for "their" consumer, manufacturers inevitably come to the system of service provision. "The purpose of such a system is to ensure the protection of intellectual property, increase competitiveness, achieve scientific priority and world recognition, and turn scientific achievements into an innovative product» (Suneeta & Koranne, 2014).

The quality customer service program helps the company retain customers and thereby reduce marketing costs. As you know, good service costs money, but annual campaigns to attract customers cost much more.

The service has a multiplier effect: it multiplies the results achieved by advertising, marketing, and sales. At the heart of this multiplier effect is a positive attitude towards the company, which is created by customers through high-quality personal service and motivates them to recommend the company to other people.

In the beauty industry, understanding the issues of «clientology», customer service quality, and knowledge of the laws and principles of customer service are of particular importance. Providing high-quality services requires significant costs, but the practice of advanced service companies proves that they will pay off many times by increasing customer satisfaction, maintaining and growing the customer base, increasing sales and profits (Khristianto, Kertahadi, & Suyadi, 2012).

Behind the success of most service companies (beauty salons, hairdressers and studios) is the commitment to effectively implement the service strategy in the strategy of enterprises. Successful implementation of the professional strategy of the service, its sales, contribute to an increase in profit and profitability exponentially, while minimizing advertising and marketing.

The service of the salon business requires constant and unflagging attention. Customer service programs should change with changing customer needs and requests. Managers and ordinary employees of beauty industry enterprises should become creators and inventors of the service (come up with new ideas and implement them) (Na-Nan, & Chalermthanakijkosol, 2011).

Today's leaders in the beauty industry need to set the task of treating customer service as a long-term strategy on a par with other business strategies. The service strategy requires the unflagging commitment of the management and the support of the staff for a long time, if the need to increase the loyalty of customers of beauty salons is ensured.

The most important long-term strategies of the service include the following:

1. Service as a product. Most consumers of beauty services do not have the necessary knowledge to correctly choose a service or product, and they want to be sure that in case of problems they will receive support and service.

2. The client is the owner of the salon.

3. Guarantee of reliability. Reliability implies constant quality service that meets all the expectations of all customers all the time. Of course, this is the ideal. However, the implementation of the customer service program really brings us closer to this ideal (Mohammad & Alhamadani, 2011).

In the face of fierce competition in the market of beauty services, the service is just a godsend for the company. The most successful salons have made a bet on service, not on prices. Indeed, competitive prices attract buyers, but not customers. Anyone can reduce the price. However, if you give customers something valuable, such as a polite, attentive, caring attitude, they will be happy to pay and come to the salon again. If a company treats its customers well, is always happy with them, and makes it clear that it values their loyalty then profit growth is natural.

High-quality service of beauty industry enterprises is the concentration of all resources and all employees of the enterprise on customer satisfaction. It is all employees, not just those who directly communicate with the client. There is an element of service in everything that every employee does in the enterprise, because in the end, any activity affects the real or perceived quality of the service purchased by the client (Na-Nan, & Chalermthanakijkosol, 2011).

The main functions of the service are to retain existing customers, attract new customers and create a need for all customers to continue cooperation with this company, enterprise and firm. The following tasks of high-quality service are distinguished:

- 1) Maintaining the customer base;

- 2) its development.

From the point of view of relationships, quality service is caring, courtesy, honesty, willingness to help, efficiency, accessibility, friendliness, knowledge, professionalism. If a company implements a service strategy, then in the field of customer service, it invariably adopts and implements in practice the so-called laws of customer service, which are as unchangeable and constant as the law of universal gravity or the laws of aerodynamics. Ignorance of these laws does not exempt you from their operation. They always work, and we constantly test their effect. The laws of customer service are a kind of philosophy that focuses on the commitment to customer satisfaction.

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